

Supplemental Information 2: Repository Resilience Project Focus Group Script

About this Resource

This supplement includes the focus group script used for the project associated with *Sutton-Kennedy, T., Crall, A., Trice, A., & Gum, J. (2026). Repository Resilience in Practice: Findings and Strategies from a Community in Crisis. Zenodo.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20617197>.

Introduction

Welcome and thank you for joining today's focus group.

My name is [Name of Interviewer]. I am the [Role, Affiliation] and am a member of the repository resilience project team.

Today we're discussing how disruptions to data repositories impact the administrators of those repositories as well as their users. This includes, but is not limited to, researchers, policy makers, emergency responders, and educators. Your insights will help shape future strategies for data preservation and resilience.

Our goals:

- To learn how you've personally experienced data loss or disruptions
- To identify what helped or hurt your ability to access and use data
- To determine what support is most needed

Permission to Record

Before we begin, I'd like to remind you that this session will be recorded.

As we mentioned in the email, the recording will only be used to help accurately capture what is said so I can analyze the data later. It will be stored securely, and only our project team will have access to it. We will not use your name in any reports, and all comments will be de-identified. I will share a link to our Data Privacy Policy again with you all in the chat [paste link into chat: <https://tesseractstrategies.org/rcs-project-data-privacy-policy/>]

You may also wish to anonymize yourself by changing your name as it displays in the Zoom window. You can do this by clicking the ellipsis next to your name and selecting "rename". I will use this name to identify you throughout the discussion.

Do I have everyone's consent to record this session? Please indicate by typing "yes" into chat. [Pause for confirmation.]

If at any point you'd prefer to pause the recording, please let me know.

[START RECORDING]

Thanks to everyone for providing their consent for recording this conversation.

Ground Rules

Let's begin with a few ground rules:

- This is a confidential and voluntary discussion. Please do not share anything outside of this space without requesting explicit permission from the individual who shared it.
- There are no right or wrong answers, just your experiences and perspectives.
- Please speak freely. Your input is invaluable. You are also welcome to build on each other's points or raise different viewpoints.

Does anyone have any questions regarding these ground rules before we get started with our discussion?

Questions

Let's start by introducing ourselves: please share a little bit about your role in repository resilience and your interest in joining today's discussion.

[Copy and paste questions into chat after they are asked]

1. Can you describe a time when a data repository you administered or relied on was disrupted or lost?
 - a. If not, are you aware of instances where this has happened, or do you have concerns about what might happen if such a disruption occurred?
2. What were the immediate and longer-term impacts of the disruption you shared?
 - a. If you haven't experienced one directly, how do you think such a disruption might affect your work or community?
 - b. How did stakeholders (e.g., users, funders) respond to the disruption?
3. For the examples shared, were there institutional or technical strategies that helped mitigate the impacts?
4. What role did personnel changes (e.g., turnover, loss of expertise, role transitions) play in the disruption or recovery process?
 - a. If you haven't faced this, how might staff capacity or expertise gaps influence your ability to respond to a disruption?
5. In your view, what supports, policies, or practices are most needed to improve repository resilience and reduce the impact of future disruptions?

We'll wrap up with one final question:

6. If you had the power to implement one policy or practice to prevent future repository loss, what would it be?

Thank you for sharing your expertise today.